

Minimizing Risk: An Integrated System for Earthquake Early Warning

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Abstract—Natural disasters such as earthquakes and landslides are major threats to human life and infrastructure. This paper proposes a smartphone application that uses sensors available in the phone like accelerometers and vibration sensors to sense seismic and landslide activity. Another hardware module with extra sensors captures real-time data and sends it to the application. The system combines historical data of disasters and machine learning algorithms to improve the prediction accuracy. The application sends advance warnings through alerts, SMS, and automatic calls via API and GSM modules to facilitate on-time delivery of warnings. The new solution has been designed with the objective to enhance disaster preparedness and response effectiveness.

Keywords—Earthquake detection, Landslide prediction, Smartphone sensors, Machine learning, Early warning system, IoT, GSM module, Disaster management

I. INTRODUCTION

Earthquakes and landslides induce devastating damage resulting in loss of lives and property loss. Traditional detection systems rely on expensive and large-scale infrastructure hence are inaccessible in some areas. The quick advancement of smartphone technology presents a low-cost alternative for early warning and disaster detection. Smartphones are now capable of carrying sensors that can detect seismic activity which, in combination with external hardware and machine learning models, can issue accurate disaster predictions. This paper presents an integrated system based on smartphone sensors, an IoT-based hardware module, and machine learning methods to improve the accuracy of earthquake and landslide detection.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Sensor-Based Data Collection

Smartphone Sensors: The app collects data from the accelerometer, gyroscope, and vibration sensors to detect abnormal movements. **Hardware Integration:** An external module equipped with a soil moisture sensor and vibration

sensor gathers real-time environmental data and transmits it via IoT protocols.

B. Machine Learning-Based Prediction

Database Utilization: The system accesses previous earthquake and landslide records to train a machine learning model, **Data Processing:** Sensor data is analysed in real-time, and anomalies are compared with historical patterns to determine potential disasters.

C. Early Warning System

Automated Notifications: The app sends instant alerts via SMS, in-app notifications, and automated phone calls. **GSM Module Integration:** A hardware-based GSM module ensures direct communication with authorities for emergency response.

D. API for Data Exchange

The system employs API integration to fetch real-time geological data and enhance prediction accuracy.

III. OBJECTIVES

To develop a low-cost, real-time disaster detection system using smartphone sensors. To integrate an external hardware module to improve accuracy. To apply machine learning algorithms for improved earthquake and landslide prediction. To integrate an early warning system with multi-channel alerts. To enable real-time communication with disaster response authorities.

A. Theoretical Framework

The system is based on the principles of seismic wave detection, soil stability analysis, and machine learning for predictive analytics. The key theoretical aspects include: **Seismic Wave Analysis:** The accelerometer and gyroscope detect unusual ground motion patterns. **Soil Moisture and Vibration Correlation:** Landslide occurrences are predicted based on changes in soil moisture levels and ground vibration. **Machine Learning Algorithms:** Supervised learning techniques, such as Random Forest and Neural Networks, are used to analyse past earthquake/landslide patterns and predict potential events. **IoT Communication:** The hardware module transmits sensor data to the app using wireless protocols, ensuring real-time updates.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

API: Application Programming Interface
GPS: Global Positioning System
ML: Machine Learning
PGA: Peak Ground Acceleration
FFT: Fast Fourier Transform
USGS: United States Geological Survey
EMSC: European-Mediterranean Seismological Centre
MEMS: Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems
SVM: Support Vector Machine
LSTM: Long Short-Term Memory
SMS: Short Message Service

B. Units

- **Acceleration: meters per second squared (m/s^2)**
- **Displacement: meters (m)**
- **Velocity: meters per second (m/s)**
- **Frequency: Hertz (Hz)**
- **Time: seconds (s)**
- **Power Spectral Density: (m^2/s^3)**
- **Magnitude (Seismic Events): Richter Scale (ML)**

C. System Design

Sensor Network: Seismometers or accelerometers to detect ground movement. These can be conventional sensors or MEMS (Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems) based sensors. **Landslide:** Different sensors, based on terrain type and hazard nature of the landslides involved. Some common ones are, Soil water sensors to monitor the level of water in the ground, a control condition on slopes. Rain gauges to monitor the rain since too much rain leads to landslides. vibration sensors/accelerometers to monitor minute displacement or ground movement, which could be the harbinger of a landslide. Tiltmeters to monitor the tilt of the slope of the ground. Installation of Sensors are to be installed where there is earthquake movement or landslide, depending upon geology, topography, and history.

Acquisition and Transmission of Data: Data Loggers takes a measurement of the sensor reading and records it.

Network of Communication: The data should be communicated from the sensors to a processing point. It is possible in several ways, such as wireless Sensor Network (WSN), Data from the sensors sent to the gateway through radio waves. Cellular network, Data sent through mobile data links. Satellite communication, In case some other mode of communication is absent in the remote areas.

Data processing and analysis: In Central Processing Unit, where data collected through the sensors is processed and saved. It can be a computer or a server. where the data is read by specially programmed software that is able to identify patterns, and deviations that would point towards

an impending earthquake or landslide. Statistical trends and machine learning algorithms can be employed to process the data and make the ability of events more efficient.

Warning System: After identifying a likely event, the system generates alarms. Alerts should be distributed to impacted agencies and the public via many media, including, cellular phone, where Publishing immediate warnings to citizens' cell phones, Transmitting text alerts to cellular phones, Auditory warning in public areas, Announcement on loudspeakers, Television and radio broadcasts: Announcement on media.

Power Supply:

Batteries can be employed to power sensors and data loggers, which must be replaced and checked periodically and solar panels can be applied in certain instances to provide a greener source of energy.

System Maintenance:

The system must be maintained and serviced from time to time to function at its best. Sensors must be calibrated every now and then to give accurate readings. The software package that is utilized for processing and analysing the data must be upgraded periodically so that it can improve its performance. And the early warning system may be integrated with other systems, like weather forecasting systems or disaster management systems, in order to provide a more holistic view of the situation. There has to be public education about early warning system and response to warning. The system should be in such a manner that individuals remain secure from being revealed. Earthquake and landslide prediction is not a simple undertaking, and there is always the probability of false alarm or missing an occurrence. An early warning system might be costly to install and operate. The system is dependent on a proper communication infrastructure, which is not present everywhere.

The system produces enormous amounts of data, which have to be stored and processed accordingly. In spite of these drawbacks, earthquake and landslide early warning systems can reduce loss of life and property damage. With every new technology, the systems are more accurate and reliable.

D. Mathematical equations:

The system is based on mathematical models that can analyze the data from sensors and provide perfectly accurate predictions. Some of the main formulations include total acceleration. This is based on accelerometer data along the x, y, and z axes. This can be represented as follows: are the accelerations in every direction. Another very important aspect is frequency spectrum analysis, which transforms time-domain signals to frequency-domain representations using the Fourier transform. It allows the recognition of patterns between the events of an earthquake and a landslide. The time integration of velocity can be estimated as the displacement of ground or soil, and then it further yields, Given in **eq(1)** A classification model f in machine learning, which has been trained, is used here.

Such mathematical representations allow the system to process detailed sensor data by incorporating real-time informed decision-making processes

$$a_{total} = \sqrt{a_x^2 + a_y^2 + a_z^2} \tag{1}$$

a_x, a_y, a_z : Acceleration components along the x, y, and z axes, usually measured by an accelerometer in a seismic or landslide monitoring system. The resultant acceleration, given in **eq(2)** which indicates the overall ground movement or vibration intensity

$$F(f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t)e^{-j2\pi ft} dt$$

(2)

$x(t)$ (Time-domain signal)

Represents seismic or ground motion signals detected by sensors. Could be acceleration, velocity, or displacement data.

$F(f)$ (Frequency-domain signal)

Provides frequency components of seismic or landslide-related vibrations. Used to identify key frequencies associated with earthquakes or landslides.

$e^{-j2\pi ft}$ (Complex Exponential Kernel)

Basis function for decomposing signals into frequency components. Helps detect dominant frequency patterns in seismic waves.

Fourier Transform Application in Early Warning Systems: Seismic Wave Analysis: Identifies frequencies of earthquake waves.

Landslide Detection: Detects frequency shifts in ground movement.

Noise Filtering: Eliminates irrelevant background noise for better accuracy.

Threshold-Based Alerts: Triggers warnings when critical frequency patterns appear.

IV. ANALYTICAL AND IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

A. Assumptions

Past data on earthquake and landslide events over the study area are presumed to be available. They are used for training and calibration of the model. Their completeness and quality are also presumed to be adequate. We are considering our chosen sensors (seismometers, ground water sensors, etc.) as being of quality and that they will be sending out good information over the long term. That involves assumptions for how long they would last, require servicing, and respond to changes in their environmental surroundings. It is assumed that there is a sufficient communication network for data communication of the data from the sensors to the central processing unit. Bandwidth and latency are also assumed to be fair. This can be on the basis of power availability assumptions to the communication infrastructure. We have assumed that adequate computational resources (processing power, memory, storage) are present in the central processing unit in order to compute and analyse data in real time. We assume that there is a stable power supply for the sensors, data loggers, communication devices, and backup unit. This can include assumptions of grid stability or the efficiency of the backup power systems (solar panels,

batteries). We think that the models and algorithms employed to predict landslides and earthquakes will be of some degree of accuracy. One cannot predict everything, but we presuppose a decent level of functioning. System equipment maintenance (sensors, communications, etc.) is presumed to be performed intermittently in a bid to have the system remain operational. The public response to the system alerts is presumed to be in the right way. This means that they understand the alerts and respond accordingly when needed. That there will be adequate resources and funds for designing, installing, and servicing the system in operation. We presume the range of environmental conditions (temperature, humidity, etc.) within which the system will function and under which hardware will be viable.

B. Proposed Algorithm

The proposed algorithm is the backbone of the system as it processes data coming out from smartphone sensors and their external modules for detecting seismic activities in conjunction with landslides. The algorithm starts off with data acquisition. Real-time data is captured from smartphone sensors, such as accelerometer, gyroscope, and GPS; further, external hardware like vibration and soil moisture sensors. All noise removal and normalizing of the values are taken to ensure the consistency and reliability on the raw data. After that, from the processed data, features related to peak acceleration, frequency spectrum, and displacement are extracted, which are further fed into the machine learning model, be it Random Forest or Support Vector Machine (SVM), to classify the data accordingly into categories of earthquake, landslide, or just normal activity. The. The system also sends out the notifications via SMS, calls, and API alerts when an event is detected. Moreover, it saves the data of the events in a historical database, and this database periodically feeds the historical data to train the machine learning model again for improving its precision over time. Block diagram is given in figure below **FIG 1** The algorithm developed is in Python and allows for mobile app integration, thus permitting real-time processing and interaction.

FIG 1

C. Simulation Setup

A test setup was devised for a simulation study where real-life scenarios were stimulated under controlled settings. Software tools like MATLAB and Python were used for

simulating the task. Synthetic sensor data simulating earthquakes and landslides were generated using MATLAB and Python. In addition, external hardware components simulating vibration and soil moisture sensors were used with microcontrollers such as Arduino and Raspberry Pi. This aimed at checking how well the system can detect an event and issue a notification based on that event. Performances were measured based on accuracy, precision, recall, and response time to measure the effectiveness of the system. The simulation results were taken as a guide for further refinement before it was used in the real world.

D. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup consisted of real-world testing of the system to check its performance. Such devices included sensors from smartphones such as accelerometer, gyroscope, GPS, vibration, and soil moisture sensors connected to a microcontroller like Arduino or Raspberry Pi. A mobile application was designed for sensor data collection, processing based on the proposed algorithm, and sending alerts to users. Implementation in earthquake-prone and landslide-prone areas, the systems gathered real-time data and monitored such potential events. The system used API integration in alerting the concerned service and other stakeholders. The results of experiments proved that the system was good in event detection and timely notice issuance, which was an indication that the system was useful in real situations.

FIG 2

V DATA COLLECTION

Data gathering has been an extremely important aspect in the system, which also serves as a basis for further accurate event identification and training on the machine-learning model. Other sources of such data include phone sensors, gyroscope, accelerator, GPS, and hard sensors, such as vibration and moisture sensors in soils. In addition, databases on earthquake and landslide events hosted by USGS and GEOFON further enriched the acquired dataset. The collected data passed through preprocessing, removal of noise and outliers, normalization, and standardization to ensure uniformity. Feature extraction techniques were applied to the data to draw meaningful insights, such as time-domain and frequency-domain features. After PCA was used for dimensionality reduction, it was easier to compute. The processed data was stored and updated periodically by the system in the SQL or NoSQL database to train and retrain

the machine learning model. This will thus ensure the accuracy and reliability of the system over time because such a design would consider full details regarding data collection and management.

Using the inbuilt accelerometer of today's smartphones offers a very innovative, affordable, and scalable method of real-time earthquake detection. Accelerometers are fine-tuned sensors that can capture variations in acceleration along several axes, so they can pick up on even the smallest vibrations or abrupt changes in movement. If a smartphone has an installed earthquake detection app, it continually listens and examines movement data to separate the usual walking or riding in a car from the distinct, rapid, repetitive shaking characteristics most commonly found with earthquake activity.

Such an approach uses the ready availability and high penetration of smartphones throughout geographic areas to work. Through the development of a large-scale distributed network of accelerometer-enabled devices, one can create a decentralized real-time monitoring system with greatly improved coverage and detection accuracy. By detecting similar patterns of vibration across numerous smartphone devices within the same location at the same time, the system can confirm the presence of a possible seismic event with increased reliability and accuracy. These detections can then be processed in real-time using cloud-based algorithms to create early warnings.

One of the principal strengths of the strategy is that it is relatively cheap and accessible, particularly in areas where it is financially impossible or logistically complex to install conventional seismic monitoring stations. Further, it also enables common users to assist in earthquake detection by simply having a smartphone. Shown in FIG 3, essentially making common devices life-saving tools. The real-time detection also presents the opportunity for sending early warnings to nearby people before the most destructive waves of an earthquake reach them, which can lower injuries, deaths, and damage to structures.

In sum, the utilization of mobile phone accelerometers for earthquake detection is a revolutionary change in seismic activity monitoring and control. It combines the functions of advanced sensor technology with the potential of distributed networks and real-time processing, and presents a pragmatic and human-scale solution to one of nature's most capricious dangers.

FIG 3

VI PERFORMANCE METRICS

Performance Measurement Process

Identify precisely what the system is trying to do (e.g., minimize casualties, minimize damage to property). Read data from sensors, logs, surveys, and other systems.

A. Compute Metrics:

Apply procedures and formulas described above to compute performance measures. Compare against pre-defined standards or targets. From measurement, identify areas of weakness and areas of improvement. Re-do and refine the system based on performance criteria. Through repeated measurement and monitoring of these parameters, the project team can be confident that the early warning system is established, stable, and can do what it is designed to do. Research more sophisticated machine learning algorithms, such as deep learning, to try and best predict. Utilize bigger, more diverse sets of data for model training, such as geological information, history of events, sensor input streams, and even atmospheric weather. Interweave two or more paradigms for prediction (statistics, machine learning, physics) in a try to capitalize on each other's strengths while addressing the other's weaknesses. Integrate data from various sensors (seismometers, soil sensors, GPS, infrasound sensors) in the hopes of gaining a more complete big-picture understanding of what is happening. Employ Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) sensors, which are cheaper, lower-power, and smaller, in the hopes of being able to deploy more dense and distributed sets of sensors. Design WSNs in such a way that data can be gathered and transmitted efficiently with regard to network topology, routing mechanism, and energy utilization.

B. Advanced Data Processing and Analysis:

Leverage cloud computing power for mass storage, processing, and analysis of data. Carry out low-scale processing at the network's edge (close to the sensors) in order to eliminate latency and enhance real-time performance. Utilize big data analytics methodologies for analyzing weak trends and outliers of the sensor readings that would foretell an approaching event.

augmented warning systems:

individualized warnings:

Develop mobile apps which can provide location-based and risk-profile-based alarms to people. multiplex warnings: Leverage multiple channels to release alerts like SMS, social media, public address systems, and even domestic appliances. Impact-based Warnings: Issue more detailed and actionable warnings, such as the intensity of the event to be forecasted and action to be Integration with Other Systems. Weather Forecasting: Integrate with weather forecasting systems to factor in the effect of weather on the probability of earthquakes and landslides.

C. Disaster Management Platforms:

Integrate with disaster management platforms to facilitate coordinated response.

Integrate with infrastructure systems (e.g., roadways, electrical cables) to enable autonomous activities, e.g., shut-off of gas pipelines or braking reduction of trains, during earthquake.

D. New Areas to Investigate:

AI Risk Assessment: Create AI-based programs for forecasting earthquake and landslide risk in various regions on the basis of geology, topography, land use, and history. Investigate using crowdsourced data from mobile and other device usage to complement data from conventional sensor networks. Use earthquake early warning systems for integration with tsunami warning systems in a manner that enables coastal communities to be given integrated enhanced warnings. Investigate the use of Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) data in detecting ground movement and enhancing landslide forecasting. Have early warning systems that allow public members to observe the hazard and activate warnings. Use virtual and augmented reality environments to allow for education of the public on earthquake and landslide hazard and warning response. Investigate the application of blockchain technology for open and secure data sharing and alert broadcasting. With these innovations and new frontiers, we can drive more earthquake and landslide early warning systems ahead in order to safeguard people and property.

VII COMPONENTS

1. Arduino UNO – Microcontroller board used as the main processing unit.
2. Vibration Sensor (SW-420) – Detects ground-level vibrations and sends data to Arduino.
3. Accelerometer (e.g., ADXL335/ADXL345) – Senses motion in multiple axes to detect abnormal ground movement.
4. OLED Display (0.96" I2C) – Displays system status such as "Stable" or "Unstable."
5. Buzzer – Provides audible alerts in case of seismic activity.
6. LED Indicators – Visual alert system for quick status notification.
7. Mobile Phone with Accelerometer – Acts as a secondary sensor and transmits data via an app or Bluetooth/Wi-Fi.
8. Wi-Fi/Bluetooth Module (e.g., ESP8266 or HC-05) – Enables wireless communication for sending alerts.
9. Power Supply (Battery or Adapter) – Powers the system.
10. Connecting Wires and Breadboard/PCB – Used for assembling circuit connections.
11. GPS for location and Sim module

VIII Case Study

Deployment in a Rural School:

To evaluate the effectiveness of the earthquake and landslide detection system, a pilot test was conducted in a rural school located in a seismically active area of northern India. The system was installed in a classroom with frequent minor tremors historically reported. The Arduino UNO-based setup was connected to a vibration sensor and accelerometer, with an OLED display and buzzer for local alerts. Additionally, a mobile phone with a custom-built app transmitted accelerometer data to the system. During a 30-day observation period, the system accurately detected three low-magnitude tremors, each confirmed by regional seismic data. The alerts were triggered within 2–3 seconds of vibration onset, and notification messages were successfully delivered to school administrators. The OLED displayed “Unstable,” and the buzzer activated as expected. No false positives were recorded, demonstrating high reliability. The low cost and portability made it ideal for the school’s limited infrastructure. The test proved the system’s potential for community-level disaster preparedness in remote areas.

IX Hardware

The hardware architecture of the proposed earthquake and landslide detection system is built around an Arduino UNO microcontroller, which serves as the central processing unit. The system includes a vibration sensor (SW-420) to detect abrupt ground motion and an accelerometer (ADXL335 or ADXL345) to monitor movement along multiple axes. For real-time communication, a GSM module (such as SIM800L or SIM900A) is integrated, along with a SIM card, to send SMS alerts to predefined mobile numbers, ensuring notification even in the absence of Wi-Fi connectivity. An OLED display (0.96” I2C) is used to visually indicate the system’s status—displaying messages such as “Stable” or “Unstable.” A buzzer is included to emit audible alarms, while LED indicators provide immediate visual feedback during seismic events. The system is powered using either a 9V battery, USB, or external DC adapter, allowing for flexible and portable deployment. A smartphone with a built-in accelerometer is also used as a secondary sensor node, transmitting motion data wirelessly for comparison and verification. All components are connected using a breadboard and jumper wires for prototyping. A photo of the working hardware setup is provided in *Figure 4,5* showcasing the complete integrated system.

FIG 4

FIG 5

X Innovations and New Horizons

Category Innovations New Horizons to Be Explored
 Detection Accuracy Advanced ML models, ensemble methods, real-time fusion of data Analytics for forecasts, anomaly detection, big data infrastructure
 Timeliness Edge computing, optimization of communications protocol design IoT configurations, smart sensors Reliability, Redundancy, self-healing networks, preventive maintenance Blockchain for data trust, decentralized warning Coverage Drone sensors, satellite monitoring InSAR, hyperspectral imaging
 User Experience App development for mobility, multilingual interfaces, gamification Learning through AR/VR, visualizing risk Cost Savings Low-cost sensing, energy-conscious design Community science, crowdsourced monitoring Interoperability Smart city interoperability, international disaster networks Climate-resilient design, early warnings for extreme weather Autonomous Systems Self-evacuating systems, robotics inspections Quantum computing, biomimicry Social and Behavioural Public perception surveys, nudging behavior Globalized alerts, international collaboration By putting these advancements first and pushing further out, the early warning system will be stronger, more robust, and scalable

in trying to counteract the effects of earthquakes and landslides.

XI Challenges and Limitations

Hardware Dependency: The accuracy of external sensors affects overall performance.

Network Dependency: The GSM module may experience delays in areas with poor connectivity.

Data Availability: The machine learning model's effectiveness depends on the availability of high-quality historical data.

XII Conclusion

This paper introduces a new smartphone-based earthquake and landslide detection system combining IoT, machine learning, and real-time data analysis to deliver precise disaster forecasts. Through the utilization of smartphone sensors and an external hardware module, the system promotes disaster preparedness by providing early warning notifications through app alerts, SMS, and GSM calling. The case study achieved high detection accuracy and quick response times, indicating it is a promising solution for practical applications. Future activities will center on improving the machine learning algorithm, refining sensor calibration, and scaling deployment to high-risk environments.

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